

High Prevalence of Cast-like Fibrin Clots Extending from the Right Ventricle to the Pulmonary Artery in 16 of 42 Necropsied Pigs: Association with Right-sided Circulatory Failure

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Abstract

During approximately one year of necropsy examinations conducted on 42 pigs that died on a single commercial farm between April 2025 and April 2026, cast-like tissue structures extending from the right ventricle to the pulmonary artery were identified in 16 cases (38.1%). These structures occupied the lumen of the pulmonary artery and, in some cases, extended into the right ventricular cavity. Many affected pigs shared common gross pathological findings, including cardiac enlargement, congestion and enlargement of the liver and spleen, and marked accumulation of bile within the gallbladder, suggesting the presence of right-sided circulatory dysfunction.

Histopathological examination of one representative specimen identified the structure as a blood clot composed predominantly of fibrin. Among the 16 affected pigs, three representative cases with different presumed etiologies were selected for detailed description, including a histopathologically confirmed case, a case associated with heat stress, and a case accompanied by severe pulmonary lesions. The possible relationship between cast-like fibrin clots and circulatory failure is discussed.

Introduction

Necropsy is an important diagnostic tool for investigating the causes of mortality in swine production systems. In some cases, the cause of death can be readily inferred from characteristic gross lesions, such as severe pulmonary pathology or intestinal hemorrhage. However, other cases lack distinctive pathological findings, making diagnosis based solely on gross examination difficult. A proportion of these cases may be attributable to physiological disturbances, including circulatory dysfunction, which are often challenging to identify during routine postmortem examination.

Circulatory failure may arise secondary to a variety of conditions in pigs, including heat stress, respiratory disease, and systemic inflammatory disorders. In recent years, increasing environmental temperatures have intensified heat stress in swine production,

potentially contributing to an increased incidence of circulatory collapse and sudden death. Despite its clinical importance, the gross pathological manifestations of circulatory failure in pigs have not been well characterized, and reports describing postmortem findings associated with circulatory dysfunction remain limited.

During routine necropsy examinations conducted on a commercial swine farm, unusual cast-like structures extending from the right ventricle into the pulmonary artery were repeatedly observed. These structures were frequently accompanied by gross lesions suggestive of impaired venous return and right-sided circulatory dysfunction. Histopathological examination of a representative specimen identified the structure as a fibrin-rich blood clot.

The objective of the present report was to describe the gross characteristics of these cast-like intravascular clots and to discuss their possible association with right-sided circulatory failure. Three representative cases with different presumed etiologies were selected for detailed description and comparison.

Materials and Methods

Necropsy records from pigs that died on a commercial swine farm between April 3, 2025 and April 13, 2026 were retrospectively reviewed. A total of 42 necropsies were examined. Cases in which cast-like structures extending from the right ventricle to the pulmonary artery were identified were selected for further evaluation. One representative specimen was submitted for histopathological examination.

Results

Table 1 summarizes the dates of death and major gross pathological findings of the heart, liver, gallbladder, and lungs in the 16 affected pigs. Cardiac enlargement, hepatic congestion and enlargement, and marked bile retention in the gallbladder were among the most frequently observed findings. Among the affected pigs, three representative cases were selected for detailed description based on their presumed underlying etiologies.

Serial No.	Date	Heart	Liver	Gallbladder	Lung	Other Findings
1	2025/4/15	No data	Congestion and enlargement	No data	No data	—
2	2025/5/9	No data	No data	No data	No remarkable lesions	—
3	2025/5/9	No data	No data	No data	APP-like lesions	—
4	2025/5/9	Enlarged	No data	No data	No data	—
5	2025/7/2	Enlarged	Congestion and enlargement	No data	Mycoplasma-associated pulmonary lesions	Yellow-white mass in the right ventricle
6	2025/7/26	No data	No data	No data	Interstitial pneumonia	—
7	2025/10/30	Pericardial effusion, enlarged	Congestion and enlargement	No data	Pale lungs	—
8	2025/10/30	Enlarged	Congestion and enlargement	Marked bile retention	No remarkable lesions	Vegetative endocarditis
9	2025/12/10	Pericardial effusion, enlarged	No data	No data	Thoracic adhesion, dark discoloration, fibrin deposition	—
10	2025/12/10	No data	Congestion and enlargement	Marked bile retention	No data	—
11	2026/3/5	No data	No data	No data	No data	—
12	2026/3/11	No data	No data	No data	APP-like lesions	—
13	2026/4/8	Pericardial effusion, shaggy heart	No data	No data	Fibrin deposition on lung surface	Enlargement of inguinal lymph nodes
14	2026/4/8	No data	No data	No data	Pale lungs	Enlargement of inguinal lymph nodes
15	2026/4/8	Enlarged	Congestion and enlargement	No data	Fibrin deposition on lung surface	Enlargement of inguinal lymph nodes
16	2026/4/13	Enlarged	No data	No data	No remarkable lesions	—

Table 1. Gross pathological findings in 16 pigs with cast-like clots extending from the right ventricle to the pulmonary artery

Case 1: Histopathologically Examined Case (Table 1, Serial No. 2)

A grower pig approximately 60 days of age was submitted for necropsy in May 2025. Gross examination revealed a localized area of hepatization-like atelectasis in the cranial lung lobe, presumed to be associated with *Mycoplasma* infection. The remaining pulmonary parenchyma retained normal elasticity, and no remarkable lesions were observed on the pleural surface.

Upon incision of the right ventricle, a cord-like tissue structure was identified. Gentle traction demonstrated that the structure extended continuously into the pulmonary artery and occupied the vascular lumen. The total length was approximately 20 cm (Figure 1). The structure was predominantly red to dark red in color, with focal whitish regions. Its surface was smooth throughout. The portion located within the right ventricle was relatively thick, gradually tapering after a constricted segment and branching distally.

Figure 1. Cast-like clot extending from the right ventricle into the pulmonary artery in Case 1. The clot measured approximately 20 cm in length and exhibited distal branching.

Case 2: Pig Found Dead During a Period of High Environmental Temperature (Table 1, Serial No. 5)

A finishing pig of unknown age was necropsied in July 2025. Gross findings included cardiac

enlargement and marked hepatic congestion with enlargement. Although hepatization-like atelectatic lesions suggestive of Mycoplasma-associated pneumonia were present in the cranial lung lobe, the remaining lung tissue retained normal elasticity and showed no remarkable pleural lesions. In addition, portions of the skeletal musculature exhibited a pale, cooked-meat appearance (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Pale discoloration of skeletal muscle observed in Case 2 during a period of high environmental temperature, suggestive of heat-related degeneration.

Upon opening the right ventricle, a yellow-white tissue-like mass measuring approximately 6 × 5 cm was identified (Figure 3). The mass occupied a substantial portion of the right ventricular cavity. It was uniformly yellow-white in color, flattened in shape, and possessed a smooth surface with preserved elasticity.

Figure 3. Yellow-white cast-like mass occupying the right ventricular cavity in Case 2.

Case 3: Replacement Gilt with Severe Pulmonary Lesions During Winter (Table 1, Serial No. 9)

A replacement gilt approximately 240 days of age was necropsied in December 2025. External examination revealed foamy nasal discharge. Gross findings included cardiac enlargement, severe congestion and enlargement of both the liver and spleen, and marked accumulation of bile within the gallbladder.

The lungs exhibited focal adhesions to the thoracic wall by fibrous strands. Diffuse fibrin deposition was observed on the pleural surface. The pulmonary parenchyma was diffusely dark in color and had markedly reduced elasticity (Figure 4A).

Following incision of the right ventricle, a cord-like tissue structure similar to that observed in Case 1 was identified. The structure closely resembled that of Case 1 in both color and morphology but was longer, measuring approximately 30 cm in length, and exhibited more extensive distal branching (Figure 4B).

Figure 4. Gross lesions observed in Case 3. (A) Lungs showing diffuse dark discoloration, fibrin deposition on the pleural surface, and markedly reduced elasticity. (B) Cast-like clot extending from the right ventricle into the pulmonary artery. The clot measured approximately 30 cm in length and exhibited extensive distal branching.

Histopathological Findings

The tissue-like structure collected from Case 1 was submitted for histopathological examination. Microscopically, the specimen consisted of a meshwork of aggregated fibrin containing numerous erythrocytes, small numbers of neutrophils, and focal bacterial colonies. Based on these findings, the structure was diagnosed as a cast-like blood clot formed within the vascular lumen.

Discussion

The 16 affected pigs, including the three representative cases described above, shared the presence of large cast-like clots occupying the right ventricle and/or pulmonary artery. In conjunction with the gross pathological findings observed at necropsy, these lesions suggested that the animals had experienced circulatory impairment prior to death.

In Case 3, severe pulmonary lesions were evident and were considered the most likely initiating factor leading to right-sided circulatory dysfunction. The associated enlargement and congestion of the heart, liver, and spleen, together with marked bile retention within the gallbladder, were consistent with the pathological progression typically observed in right-sided circulatory failure.

In contrast, no severe pulmonary lesions were identified in Cases 1 and 2, and the underlying mechanism responsible for circulatory impairment was less apparent. However, Case 2 occurred during a period in which ambient temperatures approached 35°C. In addition, skeletal muscle

exhibited a pale, cooked-meat appearance suggestive of heat-related degeneration. These findings raise the possibility that heat stress induced circulatory collapse and contributed to the development of vascular stasis.

Circulatory failure associated with heat stress represents a significant health concern in pigs because of their limited capacity for evaporative heat loss. Unlike many other species, pigs possess few functional sweat glands and therefore rely heavily on vascular mechanisms to dissipate excess body heat.

Under conditions of severe heat stress, peripheral vasodilation increases blood flow to superficial tissues in an attempt to enhance heat dissipation. However, this compensatory response may reduce perfusion of internal organs and impair the maintenance of systemic blood pressure. Reduced intestinal perfusion can compromise intestinal barrier integrity, facilitating the translocation of endotoxins into the circulation and ultimately contributing to systemic shock.

The formation of cast-like clots observed in the present cases may be explained, at least in part, by Virchow's triad, which consists of blood stasis, endothelial injury, and hypercoagulability (Bagot and Arya, 2008). Blood stasis associated with circulatory impairment was likely present in all affected pigs. In addition, severe pulmonary lesions in Case 3 and dehydration associated with heat stress in Case 2 may have contributed to endothelial injury and increased coagulation activity.

Whether these structures represented antemortem thrombi or postmortem blood clots cannot be determined with certainty. However, considering their size, distribution, and cast-like morphology, extending up to 20–30 cm within the right ventricle and pulmonary artery, it appears unlikely that they developed solely during the short postmortem interval. Therefore, circulatory impairment before death likely played an important role in their formation.

The relatively high frequency of these lesions is noteworthy. Cast-like clots were identified in 16 of 42 necropsied pigs (38.1%) over a one-year period on a single farm. Although similar structures have occasionally been observed by the author in other herds, such a high prevalence has not previously been encountered. This observation raises the possibility that farm-specific factors may have promoted clot formation.

One possible contributing factor is chronic hypoxia associated with endemic respiratory disease or suboptimal ventilation. Pigs are known to exhibit marked pulmonary vascular responses to

hypoxia, potentially resulting in pulmonary hypertension and increased right ventricular workload (Tucker et al., 1988). Such changes may contribute to the development of right-sided circulatory dysfunction.

Recent studies have also demonstrated that environmental heat stress induces ventricular-dependent biochemical alterations in the porcine heart, with the right ventricle appearing more susceptible than the left ventricle (Roths et al., 2025). This finding may further support the hypothesis that heat stress contributed to right-sided circulatory impairment in some of the present cases.

Limitations

Several limitations should be acknowledged in the present report. First, histopathological examination was performed in only one case, and therefore the exact nature of the cast-like structures observed in the remaining 15 cases could not be confirmed. Second, detailed clinical information prior to death was not consistently available, making it difficult to accurately determine the onset and progression of circulatory impairment. Third, a systematic comparison with the 26 necropsied pigs that did not exhibit similar lesions was not performed. Such comparisons may help identify factors associated with the development of these clots. Finally, the retrospective nature of the study limits the ability to establish causal relationships between circulatory dysfunction and clot formation.

Despite these limitations, the relatively high prevalence of cast-like clots observed in a single herd and their consistent association with gross findings suggestive of right-sided circulatory failure indicate that this lesion warrants further investigation.

Conclusion

Cast-like clots extending from the right ventricle to the pulmonary artery were observed in 16 of 42 necropsied pigs and were frequently associated with gross findings suggestive of right-sided circulatory failure. Although the exact pathogenesis remains unclear, these lesions may represent a useful postmortem indicator of circulatory dysfunction in pigs.

References

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